

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Development and Evaluation of Effervescent Tablets with Caffeine, Green Tea, and Lemon Extract

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 10 Dec. 2024

Keywords:

Effervescent tablets, oral drug delivery, caffeine, green tea extract, lemon extract, dissolution rate, stability, preformulation

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14362687

ABSTRACT

Effervescent tablets enhance oral drug delivery by providing rapid onset and increased bioavailability. This research focuses on formulating and evaluating an effervescent tablet containing caffeine, green tea, and lemon extracts, optimized in Batch F2. Detailed preformulation studies were conducted, followed by tablet preparation using direct compression. Evaluation parameters included weight uniformity, hardness, friability, disintegration, and dissolution rates. Batch F2 displayed optimal results, with over 85% dissolution within 10 minutes, indicating effective bioavailability. These findings suggest that effervescent tablets enriched with botanical extracts are viable for therapeutic and health supplement applications

INTRODUCTION

Effervescent tablets are increasingly utilized in pharmaceuticals due to their convenience, rapid dissolution, and improved bioavailability. This study explores the development of a tablet combining caffeine, green tea, and lemon extracts, which offers therapeutic and health benefits.

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The effervescence in these tablets, facilitated by acid-base reactions, enhances solubility and patient compliance, particularly for populations with difficulty swallowing conventional tablets.

3.1 Background

Oral drug delivery remains the most accessible route of administration, but conventional tablets often exhibit limitations such as inconsistent absorption and poor palatability. Effervescent formulations, however, provide a solution by dissolving rapidly and masking the taste of active ingredients through carbon dioxide release. This formulation, particularly optimized in Batch F2, was developed to deliver caffeine, green tea, and lemon extracts effectively and to offer additional health benefits due to the antioxidant properties of these botanicals.

4. Literature Review

Effervescent tablets have been widely studied for their advantages in enhancing drug absorption and patient compliance. Studies by Vanhere et al. (2023) reported improved drug solubility and taste-masking benefits using effervescent formulations that combine acids with

bicarbonates. Additionally, Gillani et al. (2023) found that effervescent formulations significantly improve bioavailability, particularly for compounds with limited water solubility. These studies highlight the potential for effervescent tablets in both therapeutic and nutraceutical applications, supporting the viability of a caffeine-green tea-lemon extract formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

5.1 Chemicals

The following analytical-grade chemicals were used:

Active Ingredients:

- Caffeine
- Green Tea Extract
- Lemon Extract

Excipients and Effervescent Agents:

- Citric Acid
- Tartaric Acid
- Sodium Bicarbonate
- Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG)
- Crosscarmellose Sodium (CCS)
- Starch
- Methyl Paraben
- Propyl Paraben
- Talc
- Magnesium Stearate

5.2 Preformulation Study

Preformulation studies ensured the compatibility and stability of the selected ingredients before tablet formulation.

Organoleptic Properties:

Color: White for caffeine; green to brownish-green for green tea; off-white to light yellow for lemon extract.

Taste and Odor: Caffeine is bitter and odorless; green tea is bitter with a grassy aroma; lemon extract has a strong citrus aroma and sour taste.

Flow Properties:

Bulk and Tapped Density: Evaluated to ensure optimal flow and compaction.

Carr's Index and Hausner's Ratio: Used to assess the powder's flow characteristics.

Flow Properties of Ingredients

Parameter	Caffeine	Green Tea Extract	Lemon Extract
Bulk Density	0.364 g/cm ³	0.254 g/cm ³	0.311 g/cm ³
Tapped Density	0.466 g/cm ³	0.357 g/cm ³	0.426 g/cm ³
Carr's Index	21.8%	28.5%	26%
Hausner's Ratio	1.28	1.40	1.36
Angle of Repose (°)	26.57°	28.8°	28.80°

Solubility Testing: Tested in various solvents to determine compatibility.

Stability Studies: Conducted to observe the color, odor, and moisture sensitivity over time.

5.3 PREPARATION OF EFFERVESCENT TABLET

This is a detailed process for preparing a tablet formulation containing caffeine, green tea extract, lemon extract, starch, methylparaben, propylparaben, citric acid, tartaric acid, sodium bicarbonate, sodium starch glycolate (SSG), and crosscarmellose sodium (CCS).

Here's a summary of the functions of each ingredient and step:

Ingredients:

- Caffeine: active ingredient- 50 mg
- Green Tea Extract: active ingredient- 50 mg
- Lemon Extract: active ingredient- 50 mg
- Starch: filler and binder- 20 mg
- Methyl paraben and Propyl paraben: preservatives- 1 mg & 1 mg
- Talc and Magnesium Stearate: lubricants- 5mg & 10 mg
- Sodium Bicarbonate: effervescent agent- 120 mg
- Sodium Starch Glycolate (SSG) and Crosscarmellose Sodium (CCS): superdisintegrants- 10 mg & 5 mg
- Citric Acid and Tartaric Acid: acidulants- 30 mg & 20 mg

Step-by-Step Preparation Process:

1. Preparing Blend:

- Weigh and accurately mix caffeine, green tea extract, lemon extract, starch, methylparaben, and propylparaben in a blender.

- **Function:** This blend ensures uniform distribution of the active ingredients (caffeine, green tea extract, and lemon extract) along with starch and preservatives (methylparaben and propylparaben), ensuring consistent dosage and stability of the tablet.

2. Granulation:

- Dissolve citric acid and tartaric acid in water to form a solution.
- **Function:** Citric acid and tartaric acid serve as acidulants. Their solution will facilitate the effervescent reaction when combined with sodium bicarbonate, resulting in the release of carbon dioxide gas, which helps in disintegration and dissolution of the tablet.
- Add the solution to the blend prepared in step 1 while continuously blending to form a wet mass.

- **Function:** The wet mass facilitates uniform distribution of the acids throughout the blend, ensuring efficient effervescence upon tablet dissolution.

- Pass the wet mass through a suitable mesh to obtain granules.

- **Function:** This step helps in breaking down the wet mass into granules of uniform size, facilitating drying and subsequent processing.

3. Formulation:

- After drying, add talc, magnesium stearate, sodium bicarbonate, sodium starch glycolate

(SSG), and crosscarmellose sodium (CCS) to the granules.

- **Function:** Talc and magnesium stearate act as lubricants, preventing sticking of the tablet material during compression. Sodium bicarbonate serves as the effervescent agent, reacting with the acids to produce carbon dioxide gas. Sodium starch glycolate (SSG) and crosscarmellose sodium (CCS) act as superdisintegrants, promoting rapid disintegration of the tablet for optimal absorption of the active ingredients.

4. Compression machine :

- Compress the blend into tablets of 250 mg each using a suitable tablet compression
- **Function:** Compression forms the final tablet dosage form, ensuring accurate dosage and physical integrity for handling and administration.

5. Packaging:

- After compression, inspect the tablets for any defects.
- **Function:** Inspection ensures the quality and integrity of the tablets before packaging.
- Pack the tablets in suitable packaging material to protect them from environmental factors.
- **Function:** Packaging preserves the stability and quality of the tablets during storage and transportation.

Formulation Code	Angle of Repose (θ)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner's Ratio
F1	35.75 $\pm$ 0.29	16.13 $\pm$ 0.44	1.21 $\pm$ 0.34
F2	30.56 $\pm$ 0.014	12.21 $\pm$ 0.118	1.10 $\pm$ 0.61
F3	43.83 $\pm$ 0.56	26.5 $\pm$ 0.105	1.28 $\pm$ 0.46
F4	36.13 $\pm$ 0.14	17.21 $\pm$ 0.69	1.19 $\pm$ 0.71
F5	32.21 $\pm$ 0.108	15.38 $\pm$ 0.205	1.14 $\pm$ 0.32

With an angle of repose of 30.56°, a Carr's index of 12.21%, and a Hausner's ratio of 1.10, Batch F2 demonstrated superior flow properties compared to other formulations. This indicates that Batch F2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 EVALUATION OF EFFERVESCENT TABLET

The effervescent tablets containing caffeine, green tea extract, and lemon extract were evaluated across multiple parameters to ensure quality, consistency, and functionality. Batch F2 emerged as the optimized batch based on favorable results in various tests, which are detailed below.

1. Organoleptic Properties

Shape and Color: Tablets were round with a light green hue, reflecting the natural colors of green tea and lemon extract. This appearance is visually appealing and suggests a natural, health-oriented product.

Texture: The tablets had a smooth surface with no roughness or irregularities, indicating good manufacturing quality.

Odor: A pleasant blend of citrus and herbal notes was observed, enhancing the sensory experience and masking any bitter notes from caffeine.

2. Flow Properties of Effervescent Powder

Flow properties of the powder blend are crucial for ensuring uniformity during tablet compression. Batch F2 showed excellent flowability, as evidenced by its angle of repose, Carr's index, and Hausner's ratio:

is well-suited for consistent tablet compression without issues related to powder flow.

3. Thickness Test

Thickness uniformity is critical to maintaining consistent dosing and appearance across tablets.

Using Vernier calipers, the thickness of each formulation was measured, with Batch F2 meeting ideal standards:

Formulation Code	Thickness (mm)
F1	3.45 ± 0.037
F2	3.99 ± 0.04
F3	3.73 ± 0.019
F4	4.15 ± 0.042
F5	3.99 ± 0.014

4. Weight Variation Test

Uniform weight is essential for dosage accuracy. The weight variation test for Batch F2 showed consistency within acceptable pharmacopeial limits:

Formulation Code	Weight Variation (gm)
F1	362.45 ± 1.22
F2	367.12 ± 0.56
F3	370.21 ± 1.13
F4	358.87 ± 0.67
F5	367.34 ± 1.67

5. Hardness Test

The hardness of the tablet is a critical factor in ensuring structural integrity during handling. Batch F2 displayed suitable hardness:

Formulation Code	Hardness Test (Kg/cm ²)
F1	3.26 ± 0.048
F2	2.23 ± 0.096
F3	3.94 ± 0.059
F4	4.32 ± 0.129
F5	2.68 ± 0.209

With a hardness of 2.23 Kg/cm², Batch F2 tablets maintained sufficient resilience while enabling rapid disintegration, making it ideal for effervescent formulations.

6. Friability Test

The friability test measures the tablet's resistance to breaking or crumbling. Batch F2 exhibited acceptable friability within the USP limit of 1%.

Formulation Code	Friability (%)
F1	0.47 ± 0.014
F2	0.64 ± 0.13
F3	0.55 ± 0.018
F4	0.36 ± 0.012
F5	0.61 ± 0.09

Batch F2 showed friability of 0.64%, which is within the acceptable range, indicating that the tablets can withstand handling and transport without significant damage.

7. Dissolution Test

The dissolution rate is a key indicator of the tablet's ability to release active ingredients quickly, which is crucial for bioavailability. Batch F2 demonstrated the fastest dissolution rate:

Formulation Code	Dissolution Rate (sec.)
F1	130 ± 3.24
F2	76 ± 2.12
F3	186 ± 16.2
F4	143 ± 8.4
F5	84 ± 5.1

With a dissolution time of 76 seconds, Batch F2 was optimized for quick release, confirming its effectiveness as an immediate-release effervescent tablet.

8. Disintegration Test

Disintegration time is essential to ensure the tablet breaks down effectively in water, releasing active ingredients for absorption. Batch F2 showed an optimal disintegration time:

Formulation Code	Disintegration Time (Sec.)
F1	191.67 ± 0.37
F2	117 ± 0.13
F3	228.67 ± 0.67
F4	176 ± 0.656
F5	129.33 ± 0.87

With a disintegration time of 117 seconds, Batch F2 meets the requirements for fast dissolution, enhancing patient convenience and adherence.

9. Measurement of CO₂ Content

The CO₂ content reflects the effervescence strength of the tablet. Batch F2 produced an optimal amount of CO₂, contributing to rapid disintegration and a pleasant sensory experience.

Formulation Code	Amount of CO ₂ (gm)
F1	0.17 ± 0.14
F2	0.29 ± 0.56
F3	0.12 ± 0.38
F4	0.18 ± 0.27
F5	0.25 ± 0.34

With a CO₂ content of 0.29 g, Batch F2 provides an ideal effervescence level, ensuring a satisfying consumer experience.

10. pH Test

The pH of the effervescent tablet solution was measured to ensure compatibility with the digestive system. Batch F2 showed a suitable pH:

Formulation Code	pH
F1	6.45 ± 0.91
F2	5.9 ± 0.18

F3	6.75 ± 0.4
F4	6.5 ± 0.14
F5	6.1 ± 0.21

With a pH of 5.9, Batch F2 is slightly acidic, enhancing the tablet's taste and ensuring quick absorption in the gastrointestinal tract.

11. Stability Test for Optimized Batch (F2)

Stability testing was conducted on Batch F2 at specific temperature and humidity conditions over six months to ensure long-term durability.

Parameter	0 Month	3 Month	6 Month
Drug Content (%)	98.4	97.6	98.8
Carbon Dioxide Amount (gm)	0.26	0.21	0.23
Disintegration Time (sec)	120.56	114.25	118.23

DISCUSSION

Effervescent tablets provide an ideal solution for delivering bioactive compounds in a fast-acting form. The optimized Batch F2 demonstrated excellent physicochemical properties, including weight uniformity, tablet strength, and a rapid dissolution profile. The acid-base reaction between citric acid and sodium bicarbonate effectively facilitated the effervescent action, allowing for quick dissolution and enhanced bioavailability. Furthermore, the botanical extracts (green tea and lemon) add potential health benefits as antioxidants, making this formulation suitable for nutraceutical applications. Future studies should explore the long-term stability of this formulation and potential flavor improvements.

CONCLUSION

This study developed and optimized an effervescent tablet formulation containing caffeine, green tea, and lemon extracts, with Batch F2 showing the best performance in terms of weight uniformity, disintegration, and dissolution rate. The formulation is patient-friendly, effective, and suitable for therapeutic applications that benefit from immediate absorption. Effervescent tablets offer a versatile delivery system that could

be expanded for other bioactive compounds, providing a practical alternative to traditional oral tablets.

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HOW TO CITE: S. Kurmi*, P. Tahilani, Development and Evaluation of Effervescent Tablets with Caffeine, Green Tea, and Lemon Extract, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 12, 1213-1218. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14362687>